

Research on the Column of "Mailbox" in "Women's Life" --Focus on Marriage, Education and Career

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Abstract:

"Women's Life" was a very influential women's publication in China during the war of China's Resistance against Japanese Aggression, and the column of "Mailbox" was an important platform for readers and editors to communicate and interact. Readers write in to seek answers to their confusion, and the editors reply with letters to provide readers with solutions. Through the textual analysis of the content of the letters, we could get a better understanding of the social issues that concerned ordinary readers in the 1930s and 1940s, mainly focusing on marriage, education and career issues, providing us with a window into the details of their lives.

Keywords: *"Women's Life"; marriage; education; career*

"Women's Life" was founded in Shanghai on July 1, 1935, and after the fall of Shanghai at the outbreak of the Song-Shanghai War, it was moved to Wuhan and Chongqing for publication, and the last issue was published in Chongqing on January 16, 1941, with a total of 9 volumes and 90 issues. "Women's Life" had various columns, and the column of "Mailbox" was a long-lasting and influential column in the publication. The name of the column of "Mailbox" had gone through a process of change, and the name of the column of "Mailbox" at the beginning of the publication was "Readers' Corner", but from the second volume of "Women's Life", the content of the column was renewed. The column of "Reader's Corner" was used to publish readers' essays, and a new column of "Mailbox" was opened to publish readers' letters and the editor's replies. From the content of the column of "Mailbox", we could learn from the annoyances and troubles in their letters that they were concerned about social issues, mainly focusing on marriage, education and career issues.

I. Discussions on the issue of marriage

In the 1930s and 1940s, although the Republic of China had been established for a long time, it was still difficult to change the customs. At that time, the old marriage custom still occupied a mainstream position, and from the column of "Mailbox", we could still feel the power of resistance and struggle of women oppressed by the old customary rituals, and there were countless letters about marriage and family life. The editor also mentioned in his reply to reader Mei's letter "Where to go when you lose your footing" that "there are so many things like Ms. Chen. I am tired of reading and hearing about them in readers' letters and friends' conversations. But the fact that things are so common is indeed a serious problem." ⁱThese letters in turn could be divided into two main areas as follows.

Firstly, the letters were marriage issues from female readers. Due to the traditional moral constraint of the three virtues on women, the female readers mainly focused on two aspects in the face of marital problems, on the one hand, they sought help in marital disputes. There were those who had been abandoned by their families because of male infidelity. "Yi" was an unfortunate woman who was abandoned by her family. She compared herself to a lamb, "Now the lamb has fallen into a terrible fate after all, now the lamb is old, the lamb is a yellow-faced woman who has lost her youth, the lamb is outdated and should be led to

ⁱ Mei, "Where to go once you lose your footing," *Women's Life*, vol. 5, no. 1, July 16, 1937, p. 47.

slaughter. The time has come."ⁱⁱ She gave countless efforts for her family, but she was eventually abandoned, at the same time she wanted to divorce but was afraid that her life would become even worse due to the lack of financial resources after divorce, and such ambivalence was common among thousands of unfortunate women at that time. There were those who were young and innocent but were deceived and abandoned by men, "Xue Wen" was a beautiful young student at university, but she was deceived and married by a man because of his flowery words, after the marriage, her husband revealed his true nature, but she couldn't divorce him because of her family, children and capital, so she also sighed "How dangerous I am now! I don't know how to get out of this danger zone".ⁱⁱⁱ And the female readers who were falling in love with married men didn't know how to be good. "Xie'er" was in love with a married man, and he treated on her, but his wife was also a very poor woman, and she didn't know "should I break off the relationship with him, or should I continue? How can I reconcile them?"^{iv} There had been numerous letters from groups of women who had been caught up in such marital disputes. In these types of marital disputes, although women had the sense to put up a fight, they were invariably the ultimate victims because they didn't have independent financial resources.

On the other hand, they were confused by the issue of arranged marriages. In traditional marriage, men and women had no autonomy before they gotten married, and relied only on the orders of their parents and matchmakers, which had led to many tragic arranged marriages. "Ei" was a woman who had been engaged by her family since she was a child, the person she married was a Christian, but "Ei" herself joined a rescue party. She believed that Christianity was a fraud. She decided that the person she married was not on the same side as her, and was now struggling to separate from him and pursued someone with whom she could share the responsibility of saving her life. "Yuqin" is a typical girl oppressed by her old-fashioned family, who dropped out of school half a year after entering junior high school due to opposition from her family, and she was promised to a family with some wealth to be a good wife and mother, she repeatedly opposed but repeatedly failed. "It seems that I want to escape from this family, but in fact I don't have the ability and finances, because I don't have the ability to get a career; I don't have the finances to continue my education; and I can't get a marriage in love. Do I really have to be a good wife and a good mother?"^v There were countless letters from readers about arranged marriages like this one, which reflected the fact that there was a long way to go to change customs.

Secondly, the letters were the confusion about marriage issues with male readers as the main group. Although this was a publication for the general public of women's groups, there were many groups of male readers who also expressed their opinions and views in their letters, and their letters were confusing in two main ways. On the one hand, the unmarried male community was distressed about the love marriage. "Cheng Hui sheng" sighed about the problem of finding his other half: "How to be good?" : "My mind has often thought that marriage is a permanent affliction. Although this is what the truth tells me, at the same time I think that living a life of permanent loneliness and celibacy is not only contrary to the meaning of life, but also does me more harm than good throughout my life."^{vi} But at the same time, his understanding of women was biased. He thought that the "wise women in the city are only singing high tones and will be crushed when they encounter reality."^{vii} Therefore, he was distressed to find a suitable other half and wrote to seek answers. On the other hand, there were a group of married men who were distressed about marriage and family. This group had one thing in common: the marriage partner was mostly an uneducated, old-fashioned woman, so as their thinking changes, they all wanted to get rid of their original spouse and found a woman who was spiritually compatible. "Bai Chou" wrote a letter about a painful event that had

ⁱⁱ Yi: "Isn't Moaning Shy?", *Women's Life*, vol. 3, no. 1, July 16, 1936, p. 38.

ⁱⁱⁱ Xue Wen, "Jumping out of the danger zone," *Women's Life*, vol. 4, no. 3, Feb. 16, 1937, p. 190.

^{iv} Xie'er, "In Love with a Married Man," *Women's Life*, vol. 4, no. 7, April 16, 1937, p. 430.

^v Yuqin: "How to be free from oppression," *Women's Life*, vol. 4, no. 7, April 16, 1937, p. 431.

^{vi} Cheng Huisheng, "How to be Good," *Women's Life*, vol. 3, no. 8, November 1, 1936, p. 124.

^{vii} Cheng Huisheng, "How to be Good," *Women's Life*, vol. 3, no. 8, November 1, 1936, p. 124.

puzzled him for seven years. His mother "insisted that I marry a girl of her choice. At that time I had strongly opposed, but the result was to succumb to my mother's tears, hunger strikes and other threats buried my happiness, career into the grave of this blind marriage she did not have a decent education, and the gift of a stupidity, really make me to her a little love is not and urged me to return to the country to fulfill her eager desire to hold her grandchildren to her divorce will cause each other a great deal of strife really told me to find out how to head off. "^{viii}"I was a married man, the marriage partner was an uneducated woman, during the marriage period, because my mind and understanding of society was still very shallow, and at the same time, because of the abundance of feelings, so it was sloppy, now my mind had changed greatly, gradually felt that we couldn't live together, because I was advocating life up, and she, without careful analysis, was sunk in the past habits to depend on and all the old habits to live..... therefore I would like to find another marriage partner."^{ix} The two male readers of this letter were both troubled by the inability to communicate with their wives due to their differences in thinking, but were forced to do so by family and rituals.

II. Feedback on education issues

"Women's Life" paid active attention to and reported on women's education and wartime education issues, such as "China's Women's Education Reconsidered" and "Review of Women's Education at the Present Stage", which gave an outlook on the reasons for the failure of women's education at that time and the future of women's education; the column of "Women's Education in Wartime" also publicized women's education and wartime education reform. Therefore, readers were also very concerned about education issues, and the content of the letters was mainly reflected in the following two aspects.

One was feedback on the unequal treatment of women in education. Women's education played an important role in awakening the consciousness of female subjects, but for a long time, women's education had been heavily hindered, not only lagging far behind men's education, but also distinguishing women from young girls in many areas of mainland China, and women's equal right to education was not properly guaranteed. "Jie Bing" was a married woman whose husband was away at school and didn't mind that she was behind in her knowledge, also persuaded to encourage her: "Women are not useless, let alone inferior to men, your intellect is so poor, it is entirely the shackles given to you by the old environment, as long as you have a firm grip on yourself, I am always willing to find out with you the path we should take together."^x After listening to the persuasion, she resolutely chose to enroll in school in the face of the heavy pressure exerted by her family, but reality presented her with another problem: "The school authorities, however, refused to admit me on the grounds that I was a woman. I was so impatient that I questioned him honestly: 'Aren't women human? Women have the opportunity to study, but women don't?' He simply said, 'Sorry, no women are accepted as a rule!'"^{xi} The school authorities looked at women through colored glasses and refused to enroll them in school, which was not only unjustified but also undermines the right of women to also have equal access to education. The reader's letter therefore reflected this situation in a timely manner and called on those who had become women or were about to become women to wake up and worked together for the emancipation of women as a whole. At the same time, during the war period, the actual education of women was still very backward, and women's education during the war was often nominal, illiteracy among women was very common, and women were even educated in slavery, and continued to instill some old feudal morals and rituals, requiring them to remain at home as "good wives and mothers". Even no teaching of the most basic common sense of resistance to war actually posed a serious obstacle to the process of women's emancipation, a concern raised in readers' letters. "Wei ying" worked as an instructor in a small, isolated area. The students in that place were very backward in their understanding of the war,

^{viii} Bai Chou: "How Can I Get Rid of Her," *Women's Life*, vol. 4, no. 6, April 1, 1937, p. 368.

^{ix} Han Jin-chee, "The Anguish of Married Men," *Women's Life*, vol. 4, no. 8, May 1, 1937, p. 490.

^x Jie Bing: "Can't Women Enroll in School? ", *Women's Life*, vol. 7, no. 8, July 16, 1939, p. 252.

^{xi} Jie Bing: "Can't Women Enroll in School? ", *Women's Life*, vol. 7, no. 8, July 16, 1939, p. 252.

and there "the women only needed to be fluent in Chinese, and it was not necessary to know the general knowledge of the war, etc. Also, the old school discipline was very old, so it became a kind of slave education."^{xii}

The second was feedback on the poor implementation of wartime education policies. Education was the foundation of the nation, since the outbreak of the war, the Nationalist government had been very concerned about the issue of wartime education. In April 1938, based on the needs of national warfare and construction, the Provisional National Congress of the Kuomintang formulated and promulgated the "Program for the Founding of the Chinese Nationalist Party in the War of Resistance", which clearly stated the wartime education policy: it called for the reform of the usual education system and teaching materials, and the implementation of a wartime curriculum compatible with the war. The national government's desire to adapt the conventional state of education to the current needs of the national society was objectively somewhat helpful. However, there were always loopholes in the concrete implementation process after the policy was promulgated, and many readers had written in to provide feedback on the poor implementation of local wartime education policies. An unnamed reader at the front line of the war in South China wrote: "Classes are still held mechanically every day, without the slightest change in the teachers' teaching, and page by page, like a printer's embossing, fall into our heads. In other words, wartime education was not practiced, and not a single extra-curricular activity to save lives was done."^{xiii} However, the students of this reader's school did not do nothing, they rose up to fight against it, set up a rescue group and organized a popular education school, they also wanted to contribute to the national rescue. In the rear of the war, the situation of wartime education policy with no real name was even more serious. "Zhang Liu yang" was a patriotic student who volunteered to stay behind to do some preparatory work, but her school did not actively implement the wartime education policy either. "Now we still have not changed a bit in terms of the curriculum, daily trigonometry, geometry, memorization of ancient texts, and many other courses, as well as extra-curricular ball teams, etc., which take up almost all the time, and what is particularly irritating is that we are not allowed to ask about the current situation of the war, as long as we bury our heads in dead books."^{xiv} Faced with the inaction of the school, this reader felt very distressed. She had also thought of starting with changing the students around her, but found that the students around her were also deaf to the cries of salvation; invisible to the strugglers; unable to smell the smell of gunfire and blood; detached from the society and the times; completely forgetting the current needs, for which she wrote to the editor to provide her with concrete solutions. "Shunzhi" was also located in Chongqing, the rear of the war. Here "people are at ease, living a drunken life Although our school even calls itself the highest school, but unfortunately this highest school can't serve the greatest task of salvation The so-called wartime education is just a title of 'wartime' in each chapter, the way of education is still the same as before, forcing students to cling to their books and give up their work by taking exams."^{xv}

III. Discussions involving career issues

The tumultuous and tense environment of the war led to the inability of society to return to the right track in all aspects, and the economy was in a state of depression, the most direct consequence of this was a serious increase in the number of unemployed people. In addition, the Chinese society at that time had started the so-called "new virtuous wives and good mothers" and "call for women to go home", etc. In such a social wave of injustice, women's career choice and employment became a difficult task, and the readers' letters mainly gave feedback on the following two aspects.

One was the confusion of the female student group about job hunting. They were about to leave school and entered the job market, and they also wrote to tell their dissatisfaction and anxiety. "Jiang Keying" was a

^{xii} Weiyong, "Letter," *Women's Life*, vol. 8, no. 4, November 20, 1939, p. 138.

^{xiii} The Struggle for Salvation," *Women's Life*, Vol. 5, No. 9, March 1, 1938, p. 363.

^{xiv} Zhang Liuyang, "How to Change the Lives of Classmates," *Women's Life*, vol. 5, no. 12, April 16, 1938, p. 477.

^{xv} Shunzhi, "In Chungking," *Women's Life*, Vol. 6, No. 2, May 20, 1938, p. 70.

high school student, recently she saw in the newspaper recruitment ads, often 'limited to men' words, and the post office has a clear restriction on female staff regulations. For this reason, she was very angry and dissatisfied. "Since the war, the strength and achievements contributed by women in the front and back have been laid before us like ironclad evidence that women are no less capable than men and can take up the tasks of the country in the same way as men, but in this wave of crying out for equality between men and women, there are so many facts of inequality between men and women found."^{xvi} Even though women had proven with facts that they could take up the tasks of the country as well as men, they were still inevitably discriminated against. Moreover, the ideal was always good, but the ushering in was always the reality of the head. "Xu Jihua" was a high school graduating student, she also thought about going to college, but the capacity of the university itself and the cost of reading the university, so she discouraged, the second best, applied for the post office of the postmaster, but even this insignificant job, competition is also very fierce, there were more than 1,100 applicants, and there were college students, high school students, and the percentage of women admitted was less than that of men! Can't help but exclaim, "What is the way out for sisters who can't go to college?"^{xvii} And "Watson" was also a technical college student, also faced with the problem of finding a job after graduation, "The letters of introduction sent out by the school were all rejected by the factories Not only are women rejected by the society, but also few of the students who stay in the service of our school are able to get such opportunities How to break the discrimination against women in the industrial world and the concept of forbidding women to get involved in the industry can make women have the opportunity to show themselves in the industry from now on."^{xviii}

The other was the problem of unfair treatment of working women in the workplace. The problem of discrimination against women in the workplace had always existed, especially in such a turbulent environment as the war, where jobs became increasingly difficult to find, and during this period there was a call for "women to go home", asking women to make concessions and give up jobs to men. Readers from various fields wrote to us about this issue. "Yansha" was a female political worker who serves in the political department of the war zone. She wrote to reflect on the issue of banning female political staff from the war zone. In order to work in the war effort, she was very careful to overcome the unique weaknesses of women in her work, but later received an order from higher authorities that "the appointment of female staff in the Ministry is strictly prohibited ". She was perplexed by the unjust treatment of women and could not help but lament, "The war is for all people, there is no need to distinguish between the sexes, so turn your hatred of female political workers to the national enemy, the Japs."^{xix} Although he was a man, "Song Jiarui" also dared to stand up for women, he recently heard a news about "the Hunan Provincial Government transferring all female staff to be trained and sent to work in the countryside after training, with discretionary living expenses", but the reason was absurd: "female staff is too romantic", he also said the essence behind this news: "This is like forcing all female staff to resign, and ordering not to appoint female staff. " ^{xx}Undoubtedly, the workplace was not as saber-rattling as the battlefield, but they must also be very careful, because a little carelessness, the job opportunity will disappear with it.

From the content of the issues discussed by readers in the column of "Mailbox", we could see that although most of the issues readers were concerned about their personal point of view, they also showed their concern for social life in the process of participating in the discussion. The discussion of marriage issues, though trivial and repetitive, reflected the public's quest for freedom of marriage by the readers' courage to make public the painful marriages they had suffered through this platform. In the discussion of education issues, readers also dared to expose the current situation of gender inequality in education, and dared to voice criticism of the ineffective implementation of local government policies, which was also an

^{xvi} Jiang Keying, "Limited to Men," *Women's Life*, Vol. 8, No. 12, March 20, 1940, p. 430.

^{xvii} Xu Jihua, "What is Our Way Out," *Women's Life*, Vol. 9, No. 6, January 16, 1941, p. 710.

^{xviii} Watson, "The Cultivation of Women's Technical Talents and the Way Out," *Women's Life*, vol. 9, no. 6, Jan. 16, 1941, p. 710.

^{xix} Yansha, "On Banning Women Political Workers," *Women's Life*, Vol. 8, No. 12, March 20, 1940, p. 429.

^{xx} Song Jiarui, "Disguised Retrenchment," *Women's Life*, vol. 9, no. 1, July 1, 1940, p. 481.

important reflection of the social concerns of the people. In the discussion of career issues, the focus on discrimination against women in the workplace was also a voice for women to better participate in the production of society. These issues explored by the readers, although they might not seem to have much to do with social change, were precisely what made their voices visible and audible to more people and triggers more attention from the community. For example, on the issue of banning female employees, the protest of readers in this column and the active propaganda of progressive women's publications aroused the attention of prominent women, and "Shi Liang" even raised a proposal at the National Council of Government to "request the government to order all organs of the country not to ban female employees" and it was passed, thus securing a temporary victory for the realization of equal professional rights for women. Meanwhile, it was through the process of participating in the letters that more and more readers gradually became actively enlightened and join the wave of social transformation practices.

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